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Raw Materials Quality and Additional Value of Central Sulawesi Cocoa Agroindustry on Rumah Coklat Industry in Palu, Indonesia

Author's Details:

^(1,5)Marliyah ⁽²⁾Alam Anshary ⁽³⁾Asriani ⁽⁴⁾Made Antara ⁽⁶⁾Budi Setiawan

⁽¹⁾Post Graduate Program Student, Agriculture Faculty of Tadulako University, Central Sulawesi 94118, Indonesia ^(2,3,4)Lecturer of Agriculture Faculty of Tadulako University, Central Sulawesi, Indonesia

⁽⁵⁾Lecturer of Agriculture Programme, Agriculture Faculty of Muhammadiyah University, Central Sulawesi, Indonesia ⁽⁶⁾Lecturer of Forestry Programme, Forestry Faculty of Tadulako University, Central Sulawesi, Indonesia

¹E-mail: marliyah69@gmail.com ³E-mail: asrianiuntad60@yahoo.com ⁴E-mail: yasinta90287@gmail.com ⁶E-mail: budi_pascaunmul@yahoo.com

Received Date: 16-Oct-2020

Accepted Date: 30-Nov-2020

Published Date: 31-Dec-2020

Abstract

The existence of the Rumah Coklat was expected to help increase income and added value for farmers and Small and Medium Industries (IKM) process chocolate bars into derivative products with various flavors, by providing a higher price than the price of unfermented cocoa beans into chocolate bars (Bar) at the Rumah Coklat consists of several regions, so that the quality uniformity and products needs to be tested and the added value obtained could be analyzed. This research was conducted at the Rumah Coklat from May to July 2020. The data analysis used was the determination of the quality of the cocoa seed material using SNI standards for Cocoa Beans 01-2323-2008 and Value Added Analysis using the Hayami method. The research results showed that the quality of the raw material for cocoa beans used by the Chocolate House was in accordance with the SNI Cocoa Beans quality standard: 01-2323-2008. The three sources of raw material for cocoa beans, Great A was from Sidondo and Palolo, while Great AA was raw material from the Sausu area (Parigi Moutong). The nutritional value of fat was in the range of 45 - 61 gr / 100 gr and the highest fat content was Dark Couverture products, for protein nutritional value was in the range of 7-12 gr / 100 gr and the highest protein content was Chocolate Pasta (Liquor) products, the nutritional value of carbohydrates was in the range of 27-44 gr / 100 gr and the highest was 56% Milk Chocolate products, and the highest nutritional value of sodium was in the range of 15- 100 gr / 100 gr. 56% Milk Chocolate products. For Central Sulawesi's Chocolate Pasta (Liquor) product, the added value was IDR 52,000 / kg, a value added ratio of 34.67%, a profit of IDR 186.53 / kg, a profit rate of 0.36%; 90% of Dark Chocolate products obtained added value of Rp 57,112 / kg, a value added ratio of 38.07%, a profit of Rp 22,747.32 / kg a profit rate of 39.83%; 80% of Dark Chocolate products obtained added value of IDR 54,558 / kg, a ratio of added value of 36%, a profit of IDR 42,058.13 / kg, a profit rate of 77.09%; 60% milk products obtained added value of Rp. 29,121 / kg, value added ratio of 19%, profit of Rp. 20,030 / kg, profit rate of 68.78% and 56% of milk products obtained added value of Rp. 25,698 / kg, value added ratio of 17%, profit. IDR 20,435.13 / kg, the profit rate was 79.52%. Of the five types of products produced by the Chocolate Home Industry, respectively providing the highest added value were Dark Products 90% (Rp. 57,112 / kg), Dark 80% (Rp. 54,558 / Kg), Liquor (Rp. 52,000 / kg), Milk 60% (Rp.29,121 / kg) and Milk56% (Rp.25,698 / kg). Based on Added Value Analysis of processing cocoa beans into chocolate bars (Chocolate Bar) in one production process where 43 kg of dry fermented cocoa beans were needed to produce 30 kg of chocolate bars with 5 types of processed products, namely: Liquor, Dark 90%, Dark 80%, Milk 60% and Milk 56%. It was recommended that it should apply the SNI Cocoa Beans as a whole quality standard in purchasing raw material. The raw material for cocoa beans had met the quality standards of SNI 01-2323-2008, which came from three (3) regions of raw material sources should be separated because its quality differences. The policy makers and related parties should pay serious attention to the farmer and the raw materials availability. its better if the two types production could be increased.

Keywords: quality, value added, agroindustry, Central Sulawesi cocoa

PRELIMINARY

Cocoa (*Theobroma cacao L.*) was one of the leading commodities in the Indonesian plantation sub-sector which had a very wide international market. The export market for cocoa in the form of cocoa butter included the United States and Europe, while for cocoa powder or cocoa powder for the Asia Pacific market such as Malaysia, Thailand, Japan, India and China (Hasibuan A. M, et al (2014) and Market Intelligent-ITPC (2015)). As a world cocoa bean producer, Indonesia was ranked third (430,000 tonnes) after Ivory Coast (1,480,000 tonnes) and Ghana (850,000 tonnes) (World Cocoa Foundation, 2012).

Since 2011 Indonesia had become the third largest exporter of cocoa beans in the world at 15% after Ivory Coast 38.3% and Ghana 20.2% (Davit et al, (2013); Bloomberg (2015); Effendi U et al (2017) ; Kolavalli Shashi and Marcella Vigneri (2009) and ICCO (2013)).

The agricultural sector had a fairly important role in economic activity in Indonesia, this could be seen from its contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) which was quite large, which was around 12.81% in 2018. One of the sub-sectors with quite a large potential was the sub-sector. plantation. The contribution of the plantation sub-sector to GDP was around 3.29% in 2018 or first in the agricultural sector. This sub-sector was a provider of raw materials for the industrial sector, absorbing labor and earning foreign exchange (Indonesian Cocoa Statistics, 2018).

Indonesian cocoa production continued to fluctuate from year to year so that it affects exports which were still dominated by cocoa in the form of primary commodities, namely dry cocoa beans (Basorudin, M et al (2018) and the Center for Agricultural Data and Information (2017)). Even so, the government's attention in developing the cocoa agroindustry was still very high, this was evidenced through various programs such as cocoa-based downstreaming, the Cocoa Sustainability Partnership (CSP) program, as an effort to boost the productivity of domestic cocoa farmers. In 2010 another government policy was the implementation of export duties, which could trigger an increasing trend in processed cocoa exports from 118 thousand tons in 2010 to 266 thousand tons in 2014, or an average increase of 32% every year (Maulana Arif and Fitri Kartiasih, 2017).

According to the Center for Agricultural Data and Information (2017), Central Sulawesi was a province that had the highest production among cocoa-producing provinces in Indonesia. Since 2015, cocoa production had begun to decline due to several factors, namely the presence of pest attacks, lack of maintenance of cocoa plants by farmers, the conversion of land to non-agricultural land. In Central Sulawesi, there were several cocoa producing wereas, namely Parigi Moutong Regency (31,258 tonnes), Poso (13,155 tonnes), Donggala (13,067 tonnes), Sigi (11,786 tonnes), Banggai (8,747 tonnes) and other wereas (22,638 tonnes) so that the total cacao production in Central Sulawesi reached 11,651 tonnes (Center for Agricultural Data and Information , 2017).

This high production was still in the form of dry beans, most of which were unfermented cocoa beans and had not been matched by increased production in the downstream industry, so that the added value received by farmers and industry players was still very low. In addition, farmers' interest and awareness as a provider of raw material for fermented cocoa beans was still lacking. Meanwhile, the cocoa industry really needed fermented raw materials to produce quality processed chocolate. The high and low quality of processed chocolate highly depended on the raw material for fermented cocoa beans. Industry had broad linkages, both upstream, namely in the form of increasing farmer income through higher cocoa bean prices and downstream, namely in the form of employment and expansion of the industrial sector and other service sectors (Soekartawi, 2005).

There was a transformation of the economy from a conventional economic sector to a modern one (industrialization), where developing countries were generally based on the conventional agricultural sector, which was now more commonly known as the agro-industry (Basorudin M et al, 2018). Agroindustry was a business of processing raw materials from plants and animals. Agro-industry had broad linkages, both upstream in the form of increasing farmers' income through more competitive cocoa beans prices and downstream in the form of employment and expansion of the industrial sector and other service sectors (Afounjuk, 2004; Zulfiandri and Marimin, 2012).

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The cocoa processing industry played an important role in contributing to national economic growth. The government had designated the cocoa processing industry as one of the prioritized sectors for development according to the 2015-2035 National Industrial Development Master Plan (RIPIN), which was conveyed by Minister of Industry Airlangga Hartarto at the Commemoration of Indonesian Cocoa Day 2019 in Jakarta. Furthermore, it was said that the cocoa processing industry was also part of the food and beverage industry which was a mainstay in the Making Indonesia 4.0 road map. This sector also involved a lot of small and medium industries (IKM) (Ministry of Industry, 2019).

There was a policy of the Regional Government to develop Central Sulawesi chocolate, namely by making the cocoa industry the first leading industry. Rumah Coklat was the only chocolate industry in Palu City which was owned by the Regional Government, very focused on carrying the name Central Sulawesi chocolate, which used raw materials from local cocoa beans produced by smallholder plantations into cocoa paste (Converture cocoa) in Central Sulawesi. Rumah Coklat, in running its processing industry, was still lacking in raw materials for fermented cocoa beans. The source of raw material for the Rumah Coklat came from several cocoa-producing wereas in Central Sulawesi, including Sigi Regency (Sigi Biromaru District, Sidondo Village and Palolo District), Parigi Moutong Regency (Sausu District), Regency. Of the several regions, of course the uniformity and quality of the cocoa beans purchased varied greatly, so it was deemed necessary to assess the quality of the raw material for cocoa beans used by the Chocolate House.

In this study, it was not only the quality or quality of the raw material for cocoa beans that must be considered, but the added value obtained by farmers as raw material providers, if the farmer carries out fermentation in exchange for the price of unfermented and fermented cocoa beans, there was a difference in the purchase price by the house. Chocolate. Meanwhile, to calculate the added value of fermented cocoa beans, it was processed into chocolate paste which later became chocolate. It was considered necessary to conduct a study on how much added value was obtained from processing cocoa beans into chocolate bars.

The purpose of this study was to analyze the quality of the cocoa used as raw material by the Rumah Coklat and also to analyze the added value obtained from the processing of fermented cocoa beans into chocolate paste (Converture Cocoa).

MATERIALS AN METHODS

Location and Time Research

This research was conducted from May to July 2020, where the determination of the research location was determined puIDRosely (PuIDRosive) with the consideration that Rumah Coklat was the only industry for processing local cocoa beans into chocolate paste (Couverture Cocoa) in the form of chocolate bars (Chocolate Bar) which consists of five products types (Liqour, 90% Chocolate, 80% Chocolate, 60% Milk Chocolate and 65% Milk Chocolate), which were available in Palu City. And the determination of respondents was determined puIDRosely (PuIDRosive), as many as 4 people consisting of 3 cocoa farmers as providers of raw material for cocoa beans at the Chocolate House. The data used in this study were primary data and secondary data.

Research Data

Primary data was data obtained from respondents in this case were cocoa farmers who carry out fermentation from 3 locations of raw material sources and the Rumah Coklat Head production section. Meanwhile, secondary data was data obtained from related institutions, books and literature as well as research results related to this research.

Data Analysis

The data analysis method used in this study were: To determine the quality of cocoa beans, the Indonesian National Standard (SNI) was used based on the Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture Number 51 / Permentan / OT.140 / 9/2012 dated 4 September 2012 concerning Cocoa Postharvest Guidelines, namely SNI for Cocoa Beans. 01-2323-2002. Meanwhile, to find out how much added value was obtained in the process of processing cocoa beans into chocolate paste (Converture Cocoa), Value Added Analysis using the Hayami Method 1987 was used in Asheri Vitalia Putri and Amzul Rifin (2014).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

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Rumah Coklat was established in 2014 and was inaugurated by the Minister of Industry in 2015. It is located at Jalan Setia Budi number 18 Palu City, Central Sulawesi, so the resulting chocolate product was called Central Sulawesi Chocolate. The Rumah Coklat was owned by the Regional Government, in this case it was formed by the Central Sulawesi Provincial Industry and Trade Office which was directly supervised by the Local Product Development Technical Implementation Unit so that all financing was borne by the Regional Government and the results return to the Regional Treasury. Since the establishment of Rumah Coklat until now there had been approximately 100 IKM partners with it. Rumah Coklat produced chocolate bars (Chocolate Bar) as a semi-finished ingredient to be reprocessed by IKM into various kinds of preparations and flavors. The existence of the Rumah Coklat established by the Regional Government was to support the farmers who carry out fermentation with a price difference of IDR. 8000 / kg from the prevailing market price could also empower Small and Medium Industries (IKM) which processed chocolate pasta into processed products in the form of food light or snack with a variety of flavors at a subsidized price of IDR 150,000 / kg. With the growth of IKM, it was hoped that it could absorb a lot of workforce in order to distribute income to the community. The Rumah Coklat was located on Jalan Setia Budi No. 18 Palu City, which had 8 employees consisting of the Section Head who directly oversees the Chocolate House, the Head of the Production Section, and 6 staff who had their respective duties and functions (of the six staff, 5 of them were part of the production)

Quality of Central Sulawesi Cocoa Beans

The results showed that the quality of fermented cocoa beans as raw material used by the Rumah Coklat was in accordance with the SNI standards for Cocoa Beans 01-2323-2008, could be seen in the following table: Table 1. Table of Quality Test Results of Raw Material for Fermented Cocoa Beans in a Rumah Coklat Coming from Three Different Locations.

No	Quality Criteria	Unit	Requirements	Results in the field (source of raw materials)		
				Sidondo	Palolo	Sausu
1	Fermentation Time	Days	4 - 5	4	4	4
2	Kadar Air	%	≤ 7,5	7	7,4	7
3	The seeds smell like smoke / bad smell / abnormal	No	No	No	No	No
4	Number of seeds / 100 grams	-	AA,A,B,C and S	A	A	AA
5	Broken Seeds Level	% b/b	Maximal 2	No	No	No
6	Dirt Level	% b/b	No	No	No	No
7	Object Strange Level	% b/b	No	No	No	No
8	Empty seeds	% b/b	Maximal 3	0,3	0,5	No
9	Moldy Seeds	% b/b	Maximal 3	No	No	No

Source: Primary data after processing, 2020(SNI 01-2323-2008).

Based on the results of the research on the quality test of fermented cocoa bean raw materials used by the Rumah Coklat in table 1 above, it shows that the quality criteria for fermented beans were in accordance with what had been determined by the National Standardization Agency (BSN), namely SNI for Cocoa Beans 01-2323-2008. Starting from the length of time in the fermentation process, the moisture content of the beans was still passed the SNI limit, namely the beans from Palolo had 8 moisture content, the beans had a smoky smell / foreign smell (already according to SNI for Cocoa Beans 01-2323-2008). Meanwhile, the measurement of the number of beans / 100 grams of each of the three sources of raw material for cocoa beans was included in great A (from Sidondo and Palolo) while great AA (from Sausu). Likewise, the levels of broken seeds, levels of dirt and foreign matter, moldy seeds, insect seeds, 0.3% (Sidondo) and 0.5% (Palolo) empty seeds, the levels of dirt and germinated seeds, were respectively. on the standards set by SNI. This shows that the quality of the raw material for cocoa beans used by the Rumah Coklat in its production process to produce chocolate paste (cocoa converture) had met the quality standard. Of the three raw material source whereas, it could be seen that the highest quality seed was the raw material for cocoa beans from Sausu (Parigi Moutong). However, in the processing process, the raw materials were not separated based on the source of the raw materials, but were mixed together. So it was not known whether the final product obtained was different from the three sources of raw material.

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Based on the results of the study, the quality of the raw material for cocoa beans used by the Rumah Coklat was in accordance with the BSN requirements, namely SNI for Cocoa Beans 01-2323-2008. It's just that the problem was the availability of raw material for fermented cocoa beans was still lacking, this was due to the lack of interest and knowledge of farmers in fermenting cocoa beans. So that the Rumah Coklat must had a lot of stock in order to maintain the continuity of its processed production.

The Nutritional Value of Central Sulawesi Chocolate Products

To see the nutritional value of each type of chocolate bar product obtained by Rumah Coklat, could be seen in the table below:

Table 2. Information on Nutritional Value of Laboratory Test Results for Chocolate Bar Processed Chocolate House, Year 2029.

No	Products Types	Product Nutritional Content (Serving Size 100 grams)			
		Total Fat (g)	Protein (g)	Carbohidrate (g)	Natrium (mg)
1	Liquor (Pasta Cacao	51	12	30	30
2	Dark Couverture	61	8	27	15
3	Dark Chocolate 90%	57	8	31	55
4	Milk Chocolate 60%	46	7	43	115
5	Milk Chocolate 56%	45	7	44	100

Source: Industrial Research and Development Center for Agro-Industry Center, 2019.

From the results of laboratory tests on information on the nutritional value of Central Sulawesi chocolate products with 5 types of products at the Rumah Coklat in Palu City, which was carried out by the Agro-Based Industry Calibration and Analytical Laboratories, the Industrial Research and Development Agency, the Center for Agro Industry with No. 2437 / BPPI / BBIA /LHU.1/IV/2019, indicated that the nutritional value of fat was in the range of 45 - 61 gr / 100 gr and the highest fat content was Dark Couverture products, for protein nutritional value was in the range of 7-12 gr / 100gr and the highest protein content was Licor products (Chocolate Pasta), the nutritional value of carbohydrates was in the range of 27-44 gr / 100 gr and the highest was 56% Milk Chocolate products, and the highest nutritional value of sodium was in the range of 15- 100 gr / 100gr the highest was 56% Milk Chocolate products.

Additional Value Analysis

The processing of cocoa beans into chocolate paste was then packed into chocolate bars (Chocolate Bar). In one production process it required 43 kg of dry fermented cocoa beans to produce 30 kg of pure chocolate paste (Chocolate Converture), then added with several types of auxiliary materials to produce five types of products, namely Liquor Chocolate, 90% Dark Chocolate, 80% Dark Chocolate, 60% Milk Chocolate and 56% Milk Chocolate. In one production process, each of the five types of products was produced in different quantities, adjusted to the number of requests for each type of product. The type of product that was mostly produced was Chocolate Milk 56% as much as 14 kg, Milk 60% (8 kg), Dark 80% (5 kg), Dark 90% (2 kg) and the least was Liquor (1 kg).

The results of the Value Added analysis of the five types of Central Sulawesi Chocolate products could be seen in the following table:

Table 3. Calculation of Value Added Chocolate Liquor at Rumah Coklat in Palu City

Variable	Value Calculated
1 Output, Input and Price	
1) Output (Chocolate Pasta (Liquor) (Kg))	1
2) Input (Cocoa Beans (Kg))	2
3) Labor (HOK)	1
4) Conversion Factor (Chocolate Pasta)	1
5) Labor Coefficient (HOK)	0,5181
6) Output Prices (IDR/Kg)	150.000

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7)	Average Direct Labor Wage (IDR / year)	100.000
2	Income and Profits	
8)	Raw Material Prices (IDR / Kg)	48000
9)	Other Input Contribution (IDR /Kg)	50.000
10)	Output Price (IDR / Kg)	150000
11)	a. Value-added (IDR/Kg)	52000
	b. Value Added Ratio (%)	34,67
12)	a. Direct Labor Income (IDR)	51813,47
	b. Labor Share (%)	99,64
13)	a. Profit (IDR/Kg)	186,53
	b. Profit Rate (%)	0,36
3	Remuneration of Production Factors Owner	
14)	Margin (IDR/Kg)	102.000
	a. Direct Labor Income (%)	50,798
	b. Other Input Contribution (%)	49,02
	c. Business Owner's Profits (%)	0,18

Source: Primary Data After Processing, 2020

Table 4. Calculation of the Value Added of 90% Chocolate Dark Products at Chocolate House in Palu City

No.	Variable	Value Calculated
1	Output, Input, and Price	
1)	Output (Dark Chocolate 90%(Kg))	2
2)	Input (Cocoa Beans (Kg))	3
3)	Labor (HOK)	1
4)	Conversion Factor (Dark Chocolate 90%)	1
5)	Labor Coefficient (HOK)	0,3436
6)	Output Prices (IDR/Kg)	150.000
7)	Average Direct Labor Wage (IDR / year)	100.000
2	Income and Profits	
8)	Raw Material Prices (IDR / Kg)	48000
9)	Other Input Contribution (IDR /Kg)	44.888
10)	Output Price (IDR / Kg)	150000
11)	a. Value-added (IDR/Kg)	57112
	b. Value Added Ratio (%)	38,07

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12)	a. Direct Labor Income (IDR)	34364,26
	b. Labor Share (%)	60,17
13)	a. Profit (IDR/Kg)	22747,32
	b. Profit Rate (%)	39,83
3	Remuneration of Production Factors Owner	
14)	Margin (IDR/Kg)	102000
	a. Direct Labor Income (%)	33,690
	b. Other Input Contribution (%)	44,01
	c. Business Owner's Profits (%)	22,30

Source: Primary Data After Processing, 2020

Table 5. Calculation of the Value Added of 80% Chocolate Products in Rumah Coklat in Palu City

No.	Variable	Value Calculated
1	Output, Input, and Price	
1)	Output (Dark Chocolate 90%(Kg))	5
2)	Input (Cocoa Beans (Kg))	8
3)	Labor (HOK)	1
4)	Conversion Factor (Dark Chocolate 90%)	1
5)	Labor Coefficient (HOK)	0,1250
6)	Output Prices (IDR/Kg)	150.000
7)	Average Direct Labor Wage (IDR / year)	100.000
2	Income and Profits	
8)	Raw Material Prices (IDR / Kg)	48.000
9)	Other Input Contribution (IDR /Kg)	47.442
10)	Output Price (IDR / Kg)	150.000
11)	a. Value-added (IDR/Kg)	54.558
	b. Value Added Ratio (%)	36
12)	a. Direct Labor Income (IDR)	12.500
	b. Labor Share (%)	22,91
13)	a. Profit (IDR/Kg)	42.058,13
	b. Profit Rate (%)	77,09
3	Remuneration of Production Factors Owner	
14)	Margin (IDR/Kg)	102.000
	a. Direct Labor Income (%)	12,255
	b. Other Input Contribution (%)	46,51
	c. Business Owner's Profits (%)	41,23

Source: Primary Data After Processing, 2020

Table 6. Calculation of the Added Value of 60% Chocolate Products at Rumah Coklat in Palu City

No.	Variable	Value Calculated
1	Output, Input, and Price	
1)	Output (Dark Chocolate 90%(Kg))	8
2)	Input (Cocoa Beans (Kg))	11

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3)	Labor (HOK)	1
4)	Conversion Factor (Dark Chocolate 90%)	1
5)	Labor Coefficient (HOK)	0,0909
6)	Output Prices (IDR/Kg)	150.000
7)	Average Direct Labor Wage (IDR / year)	100.000
2	Income and Profits	
8)	Raw Material Prices (IDR / Kg)	48.000
9)	Other Input Contribution (IDR /Kg)	72.879
10)	Output Price (IDR / Kg)	150.000
11)	a. Value-added (IDR/Kg)	29.121
	b. Value Added Ratio (%)	19
12)	a. Direct Labor Income (IDR)	9.091
	b. Labor Share (%)	31,22
13)	a. Profit (IDR/Kg)	20.030,00
	b. Profit Rate (%)	68,78
3	Remuneration of Production Factors Owner	
14)	Margin (IDR/Kg)	102.000
a.	Direct Labor Income (%)	8,913
b.	Other Input Contribution (%)	71,45
c.	Business Owner's Profits (%)	19,64

Source: Primary Data After Processing, 2020

Table 7. Calculation of Added Value of Chocolate Milk Products 56%

No.	Variable	Value Calculated
1	Output, Input, and Price	
1)	Output (Dark Chocolate 90%(Kg))	14
2)	Input (Cocoa Beans (Kg))	19
3)	Labor (HOK)	1
4)	Conversion Factor (Dark Chocolate 90%)	1
5)	Labor Coefficient (HOK)	0,0526
6)	Output Prices (IDR/Kg)	150.000
7)	Average Direct Labor Wage (IDR / year)	100.000
2	Income and Profits	
8)	Raw Material Prices (IDR / Kg)	48.000
9)	Other Input Contribution (IDR /Kg)	76.302
10)	Output Price (IDR / Kg)	150.000
11)	a. Value-added (IDR/Kg)	25.698
	b. Value Added Ratio (%)	17
12)	a. Direct Labor Income (IDR)	5.263
	b. Labor Share (%)	20,48
13)	a. Profit (IDR/Kg)	20.435,13
	b. Profit Rate (%)	79,52
3	Remuneration of Production Factors Owner	

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14) Margin (IDR/Kg)	102.000
a. Direct Labor Income (%)	5,160
b. Other Input Contribution (%)	74,81
c. Business Owner's Profits (%)	20,03

Source: Primary Data After Processing, 2020

Based on the results of the value added analysis using the Hayami Method, the raw materials for fermented cocoa beans into chocolate paste (Converture) which produce 5 types of products were as follows:

1. Pure Chocolate Paste Products (Liquor)

To produce 1 kg of output, 2 kg of input was used, the amount of labor used was 1 (HOK). If the input price was IDR 48,000 / kg the output price was IDR 150,000 / kg, other input contributions were not available, then the total added value for one production was IDR 52,000 / kg (Value Added Ratio 68.00%), direct labor income amount was to IDR 51,813.47 (share of workforce 99.64%) while the profit was IDR 186.53 / kg (Profit rate of IDR 0.36%). Distribution of production factors remuneration: Direct Labor Income (50.798%), Contribution of other Inputs (49.02%) and Business Owner's Profits (0.18%). (Table 3)

2. Dark Chocolate Products 90%

To produce 2 kg of output, an input of 3 kg was used. So that the value of the conversion factor was 1, the labor coefficient was 0.3436. If the input price was IDR 48,000 / kg, the output price was IDR 150,000 / kg, other input contributions were IDR 44,888, then you would get an added value of IDR 57,112 / kg (value added ratio 38.07%), direct labor income IDR 34.364,26 (labor sharing was 60.17%) while the profit was IDR 22,747.32 / kg (Profit Rate 39.83%). Distribution of remuneration for production factors: Direct Labor Income (33.690%), Contribution of other Inputs (44.01%) and Business Owner's Profits (22.30%). (Table 4)

3. Dark Chocolate Products 80%

To produce an output of 5 kg, an input of 8 kg was required, so a conversion value of 1. If the raw material price was IDR 48,000 / kg, the output price was IDR 150,000 / kg and other input contributions were IDR 47,442, then you would get an added value of IDR 54,558 / kg (Value Added Ratio 36%), Direct labor income IDR 12,500 (Workforce share 22.91%), Profits IDR 42,058.13 / kg (Profit Rate 77.09%). Distribution of remuneration for production factors: Direct Labor Income (12.255%), contribution of other Inputs (46.51%) and Business Owner's Profits (41.23%). (Table 5)

4. Milk Chocolate Products 60%

To produce an output of 8 kg, an input of 11 kg was required, so a conversion value of 1. If the raw material price was Rp. 48,000 / kg, the output price was Rp. 150,000 / kg, the other input contribution was Rp. 29,121 / kg (Value Added Ratio IDR 19%). Direct labor income Rp. 9,091 (Share of labor 31.22%) Profit earned was Rp. 20,030 / kg (Profit rate 68.78%). Distribution of compensation for production factors: Direct Labor Income (8.913%), Contribution Other inputs (71.45%) and Business Owner's Profits (19.64%). (Table 6).

5. Milk Chocolate Products 56%

To produce an output of 14 kg, an input of 19 kg was required, so a conversion value of 1. If the raw material price was IDR 48,000 / kg, the output price was IDR 150,000 / kg other input contribution was IDR 76,302 / kg, then the added value was obtained IDR 25,698 / kg (Value Added Ratio IDR 17%). Direct labor income was Rp 5,263 (share of the workforce was 20.48%), the profit earned was Rp. 20,435.13 / kg (Profit Rate 79.52%). Distribution of production factors remuneration: Direct Labor Income (5.160%), Contribution of Other Inputs (74.81%) and Business Owner's Profits (20.03%). (Table 7)

CONCLUSSION

The quality of the raw material for cocoa beans used by the Chocolate House was in accordance with the SNI Cocoa Beans quality standard: 01-2323-2008, starting from the duration and fermentation process, the moisture content of the beans, the weight of the beans / 100gr, the content of moldy beans, the content of empty beans, Grain content with smoky / foreign odor, impurity content, foreign object seed content, based on bean weight / 100 grams, of the three sources of raw material for cocoa beans, Great A was from Sidondo and Palolo, while Great AA was raw material from the Sausu area (Parigi Moutong).

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Laboratory test results of Central Sulawesi Chocolate processed products showed that the nutritional value of fat was in the range of 45 - 61 gr / 100 gr and the highest fat content was Dark Couverture products, for protein nutritional value was in the range of 7-12 gr / 100 gr and the highest protein content was Chocolate Pasta (Liquor) products, the nutritional value of carbohydrates was in the range of 27-44 gr / 100 gr and the highest was 56% Milk Chocolate products, and the highest nutritional value of sodium was in the range of 15-100 gr / 100 gr. 56% Milk Chocolate products.

For Central Sulawesi's Chocolate Pasta (Liquor) product, the added value was IDR 52,000 / kg, a value added ratio of 34.67%, a profit of IDR 186.53 / kg, a profit rate of 0.36%; 90% of Dark Chocolate products obtained added value of Rp 57,112 / kg, a value added ratio of 38.07%, a profit of Rp 22,747.32 / kg a profit rate of 39.83%; 80% of Dark Chocolate products obtained added value of IDR 54,558 / kg, a ratio of added value of 36%, a profit of IDR 42,058.13 / kg, a profit rate of 77.09%; 60% milk products obtained added value of Rp. 29,121 / kg, value added ratio of 19%, profit of Rp. 20,030 / kg, profit rate of 68.78% and 56% of milk products obtained added value of Rp. 25,698 / kg, value added ratio of 17%, profit. IDR 20,435.13 / kg, the profit rate was 79.52%. Of the five types of products produced by the Chocolate Home Industry, respectively providing the highest added value were Dark Products 90% (Rp. 57,112 / kg), Dark 80% (Rp. 54,558 / Kg), Liquor (Rp. 52,000 / kg), Milk 60% (Rp.29,121 / kg) and Milk56% (Rp.25,698 / kg).

SUGGESTION

To produce quality processed products, the Chocolate House should apply the SNI Cocoa Beans as a whole quality standard in purchasing raw materials, so that the farmers really do post-harvest cocoa correctly and in accordance with the applicable standards. Based on the results of the quality test, the raw material for cocoa beans had met the quality standards of SNI 01-2323-2008, which came from three (3) regions of raw material sources, but no separation of raw materials based on their source in the processing was recommended, so it was recommended further processing, its better to separate because the quality of the three sources of raw material was different, so it could be seen whether there were differences in the processed product. It was recommended that policy makers and related parties pay serious attention so that farmers could ferment cocoa in order to maintain the continuity of availability of quality raw materials. Based on the results of the analysis of added value obtained for five types of processed products, the types of products that had total added value in 2019 and high profits were 80% Dark Chocolate and 60% Milk Chocolate, thus its better if the production amount of the two types of products could be increased.

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